

Legal/Ethical Paper affecting Older Adults and Nurse

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Introduction

Dilemma is considered as a major problem that is responsible to originate two difficult possibilities. Both of these possibilities are impossible to be accepted. A number of idioms have been used for dilemma. The most common idiom “between Scylla and charybdis” is used as an alternative for the term dilemma. Moreover, another idiom “Lesser of two evils” is also considered as a synonym for Dilemma. A number of studies have been conducted to know about the legal and ethical issues of the dilemma, which showed that dilemma is responsible to derive two serious unacceptable conditions.

Discussion

Dilemma

There are several types of dilemmas that are supposed to be very important for our generation. Double bind is a major type of dilemmas that refers to the emotionally distressing dilemma achieved through communication. In this dilemma, a person receives 2 or more than two conflicting messages, and both messages are negating each other. The entire scenario is responsible for the confusion of an individual. It will create a situation in which one message will manipulate the other message successfully. This type of dilemma was described by Gregory Bateson. Another type of dilemma is ethical dilemma. It is a complex scenario, which refers to the apparent mental conflicts. These mental conflicts are between moral imperative, which refers to the obeying of the results. Extortion is also considered as the type of dilemma, which confers to the criminal offense to get money or property. It is similar to kidnapping for any resource. Extortion will give rise to two conditions, and both of them will be unacceptable for the victims.

Fairness dilemmas are another major type of the dilemma, which refers to the groups who faced the situation by making decisions (Mahmood, Schwatz, Kurrup, Sharp, Hands, & Moody, 2013).

This decision making will turn entire situation in the very confusing factors. Hobson's choice is also considered as the dilemma, which refers to the free choice of giving an option. The option is too difficult to be accepted. Morton's fork is another type of dilemma that refers to the specious piece of reasons of contradictory arguments. This type was originated by John Morton. Prisoner's dilemma is another type of dilemma, which was originated from the game theory. This type of dilemma refers to the non-cooperation between two individuals. Samaritan's dilemma is another major type which refers to act of charity. This dilemma was described by Buchanan. The dilemma refers to the choice that is taken between improving one's condition and providing charity. Sophie's choice is another type of dilemma, which refers to the choice between two things or person that will result in the destruction of one person. Zungzwang is a Chinese word that is used for dilemma and is responsible for the activity of chess. Zungzwang described that one have to move and destroy other when the other is unable to move (Mahmood, Schwatz, Kurrup, Sharp, Hands, & Moody, 2013).

Older adults and nurses are more prominent to fact all the types of dilemma. Dilemmas are also prominent to the teenagers due to lack of experience. Ethical dilemmas, that are also known as moral dilemmas, are the conditions in there are two options present which is impossible to be reacted. In these cases, personal and societal guidelines will not do any major help for the older adults and nurses. There are many situation and case scenarios that are described by studies to show the confusions occurred by dilemma. There was a case scenario that was based on Michael and his two friends, Roger and Daniel. Roger started dating with a lady named Phyllis. Michael observed that the lady is the wife of his second friend Daniel. Now

Michael is in a great confusion that if he told the story to Daniel then he will kill Roger. If he didn't say anything to Daniel, then Roger will get marry with the wife of Daniel. This is a dilemma in which Michael has no any acceptable option (Holmberg, Flum, West, Zhang, Qamili, & Punnett, 2013).

Solutions

A number of studies were conducted to derive the possible solutions to reduce the option of dilemma. These studies have evaluated the effectiveness of solutions that was suggested by groups and society. Moreover, the studies have also revealed that the groups' suggestions have enough potential to solve the problems of dilemma. The major suggestion was regarding the better defense system. The government should provide complete security to the older people and adults especially for the reason of extortion. Furthermore, proper communication or excellent communication skills are extremely necessary to reduce the extent of dilemma. Another study has revealed that the better communication skills will surely clear all the confusions in the scenario. Furthermore, studies have shoed that appropriate decision making is another important approach to reduce the extent of dilemma. Older people and nurses have to use these changes and solution to cope with these types of conditions (Roberts & Grubb, 2013).

Conclusion

Dilemma is that condition, which is responsible to originate two extremely difficult possibilities. There are various types of dilemmas that are responsible to make complex situations for older adults and nurses. Evidence based recommendations and interventions should be used for effective outcomes.

References

- Holmberg, M. D., Flum, M., West, C., Zhang, Y., Qamili, S., & Punnett, L. (2013). Nursing Assistants' Dilemma: Caregiver Versus Caretaker. *Hospital topics*, *91*(1), 1-8. Retrieved from <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00185868.2013.757953#.UnAHnFdg-mA>
- Mahmood, F. S., Schwatz, E., Kurrup, S., Sharp, C., Hands, G., & Moody, A. (2013). A diagnostic dilemma: differentiating between granulomatosis with polyangiitis and tuberculosis. *Clinical Medicine*, *13*(4), 411-413. Retrieved from <http://rcpjjournal.org/content/13/4/411.short>
- Roberts, R. K., & Grubb, P. L. (2013). The Consequences of Nursing Stress and Need for Integrated Solutions. *Rehabilitation Nursing*. Retrieved from <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/rnj.97/abstract?deniedAccessCustomisedMessage=&userIsAuthenticated=false>